

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DIMINUTIVE SUFFIXES OF NOUNS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Annotation: this article aims to analyze and compare inflectional and diminutive suffixes of nouns in both English and Uzbek languages by the help of several examples in both languages.

Key words: affix, inflectional, diminutive, plurality.

Аннотация: данная статья направлена на анализ и сравнение словоизменятельных и уменьшительно-ласкательных суффиксов существительных в английском и узбекском языках с помощью нескольких примеров в обоих языках.

Ключевые слова: аффикс, флективный, уменьшительно-ласкательный, множественное число.

In linguistics, an affix is a morpheme that is attached to a word stem to form a new word or word form. Affixes may be derivational, like English *-ness* and *pre-*, or inflectional, like English plural *-s* and past tense *-ed*. They are bound morphemes by definition; prefixes and suffixes may be separable affixes. This article discusses types of suffixes of nouns in both languages. Derivational affixes help to create new words. For example, *teach+er*, *improve+ment*, *friend+ship*.

Inflectional affixes can play a pivotal role to make a sentence. For example, *I have read **three** books.*

Inflectional affixes do not change the main meaning of the words, they aimed to form and display grammatical categories and characteristics of words. There are eight inflectional suffixes in English and two of them belong to nouns: **inflectional morphemes of nouns** and **possessives**.

Morpheme	Function	Example
-s	Plurality (means more than one)	Pens, books, phones
's	Possessives (means ownership)	John's book

Possessives can be formed by adding affix **-s** at the end of the nouns with apostrophe ('). The apostrophe should be used between word and affix if the word is singular. For example: *John's house; Friend's car.*

But if the word has an affix of plurality, apostrophe must be used after the affix. For example: *Ladies' shoes; Parents' house.*

If the word's plurality formed by changing the root of the word, apostrophe should be used between the word and affix. For example, *Children's book; people's car*

Plurality. In English we can form plurality by the help of suffix **-s**. For example, *Boy – boys; Book – books.* However, some of irregular have special formation, *Person – people; child – children.* Additionally, some of nouns which are borrowed from Latin and Old Greek have their own singular and plural forms, *Phenomenon – phenomena; curricula – curriculums* and etc.

Inflectional suffixes of nouns in Uzbek. If the affix establishes additional meaning to the word without changing the denotational meaning, it is called inflectional affixes in the Uzbek language. For example, *kitob(book) – kitoblar(books)*. The word “*kitob*” is singular noun in Uzbek language and it is a

name of educational tool.

The word “*kitoblar*” is a plural noun in Uzbek language and it is a name of educational tool too.

The following examples show that difference between the words is in the number, the meaning is still similar (educational tool in both examples). The table below analyses inflectional affixes of nouns in both Uzbek and English languages:

Affix	Meaning	Example
-cha; -choq; chak	Diminutive meaning <i>(A suffix which is added to a word to show affection or to indicate that something is small)</i>	Kitobcha, kelinchak, qo'zichoq
-jon; -xon; - oy; -bek; - gina; - loq	<i>(to show an affection)</i>	Onajon; Bonuxon Oydinoy; Odilbek; qizaloq; bolagina;
-lar	Plurality <i>(means more than one)</i>	Gullar
-niki	Possessives <i>(means ownership)</i>	Meniki
-gacha	<i>(to describe duration and distance)</i>	Uygacha
-lar	<i>(to show the regard)</i>	Dadamlar, Akamlar

Accordingly, in English inflectional suffixes do not contain diminutive suffixes. But it doesn't mean absence of them. In English six below-mentioned diminutive suffixes can be found. In fact, there are more than six but currently most of them are inseparable and may be viewed as a part of the word, for example, suffix *-le*. During the Old English period people used to utilize *pudd* instead of *puddle*. Nowadays it is studied as an inseparable word.

No	Suffix	English	Uzbek
1	-ie/-i/-y	Dog → doggy	It/kuchuk → kuchukcha
2	-ette	Cigar → Cigarette	Sigara → sigaretta
3	-kin	Lamb+kin → lambkin	Qo'zichoq, yosh bola (ko'chma ma'noda)
4	-ling	Duck → duckling	O'rdak → o'rdakcha
5	-et	Circle → Circlet	aylana → kichik aylana
6	-let	Pig → piglet	Cho'chqa → cho'chqacha

As above mentioned, affixes are divided into two or eight types of affixes can be seen as inflectional. Therefore, Diminutive suffixes belong to Derivational type of suffixes in English. However, in Uzbek these suffixes are studied as inflectional suffixes.

As a conclusion, we can say that in both languages there are some affixes and suffixes of nouns that have the same in some cases, different functions. It is highly recommended to study all types of affixes, suffixes and prefixes of nouns attentively with all examples to compare them in both languages.

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